

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Field screening of hybrids for the second crop in acid sulfate soils of South China

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We screened acid-tolerant hybrids for the second crop in acid sulfate soils (Table 1) of Duanfen and Wencun, Taishan County, Guangdong Province, in 1985.

At Duanfen, 18 varieties were tested

Table 1. Characteristics of the acid sulfate soils in Duanfen and Wencun, South China, 1985.

Item	Location	
	Duanfen	Wencun
pH (H ₂ O)	3.85	3.71
pH (KCl)	3.17	3.23
Total N (%)	0.22	0.17
Organic C (%)	3.13	2.16
Available P (Olsen, ppm)	1.6	4.4
Exchangeable K (meq/100 g)	0.29	0.45
Available Zn (ppm) (0.05 N HCl)	7.8	8.1
Water soluble SO ₄ (meq/100 g)	0.44	1.28
Active Fe (%)	2.70	2.49
Active Mn (ppm)	20.1	19.5
Particle size (%)		
Sand (2-0.005 mm)	6.6	22.7
Silt (0.05-0.001 mm)	62.9	58.2
Clay (<0.001 mm)	30.4	19.1

under 2 fertilizer treatments: with (1.6 t CaO/ha) and without. Limed or not, Shanyou 63 yielded best, followed by Qingyouzao, Ganghuaqinglan Fo, and Shanyou 36 without liming (Table 2). Because early high rainfall might have decreased soil acidity, only some varieties showed slight Fe toxicity in the late growth stage and the difference between the fertilizer treatments was not significant. In general, most hybrids

tested adapted to the soil.

In Wencun, 31 rice varieties were screened with NPK fertilizers. The varieties suffered more severe Fe toxicity in late growth stage. Many grains on panicles were empty in 21 varieties (Table 3).

The yield variation in Wencun was affected by percentage filled spikelets rather than straw weight, panicle numbers, and grains/panicle. □

Table 2. Grain yield of second crop of rice screened in acid sulfate soil at Duanfen, South China, 1985.

Tested rice		Grain yield			
Variety	Type ^a	Without liming		With liming	
		kg/plot	Rank	kg/plot	Rank
Shanyou 63	HV	1.00	1	1.04	1
Qingyouzao	HV	0.98	2	0.82	4
Ganghuaqinglan Fo	HV	0.95	3	0.81	5
Shanyou 36	HV	0.93	4	0.87	3
Shanyou 2	HV	0.89	5	0.77	8
Shanyouxuan 30	HV	0.89	5	0.93	2
Ce 64	RV	0.85	6	0.67	10
Qiuzhongai	RV	0.81	7	0.67	10
Zhubao 384	RV	0.76	8	0.82	4
Shanyou 64	HV	0.73	9	0.79	7
V-you 35	HV	0.72	10	0.63	12
Wanhuaai 1	RV	0.72	10	0.75	9
Qinghuaai 6	RV	0.72	10	0.77	8
Gangbaiai	RV	0.71	11	0.65	11
Qinghuaai	RV	0.68	12	0.80	6
Guishanai	RV	0.66	13	0.62	13
Liuyou 2	HV	0.66	13	0.61	14
Xiangaizao 9	RV	0.33	14	0.30	15

^aHV = hybrid variety, RV = regular variety.

Table 3. Field screening of second crop rice in acid sulfate soil at Wencun, South China, 1985.

Tested rice		Growth period (d)	Dry straw wt (kg/plot)	Av panicles/plant	Grains/panicle	Ripe state	Filled spikelets (%)	Grain yield (kg/plot)	Grain yield rank
Variety	Type ^a								
Chanjiang 204	RV	147	2.87	10.5	95.4	Better	68.0	2.01	1
Qinghuaai 6	RV	141	2.05	8.4	91.6	Better	67.3	1.80	2
Ganghuaqinglan Fo	HV	141	1.74	10.0	80.1	Better	62.3	1.75	3
Ciuzhongai	RV	141	1.75	8.1	123.0	Better	67.0	1.60	4
Zhubao 384	RV	139	2.07	8.8	75.3	Better	77.9	1.54	5
IR54	IV	138	2.65	9.2	85.9	General	53.7	1.36	6
IR4422-480-2-3-3	IV	139	2.88	7.6	86.8	General	46.2	1.20	7
IR46	IV	139	2.82	8.9	106.5	General	52.4	1.16	8
Gangbaiai	RV	137	2.03	10.5	72.8	General	50.3	1.10	9
IR32307-107-3-2-2	IV	134	1.97	10.7	101.9	General	41.2	1.07	10
Shanyou 35	HV	131	1.87	11.6	76.2	GWFR ^b	27.6	0.83	11
IR28228-119-2	IV	143	3.02	11.1	107.7	GWFR	14.9	0.81	12

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Table continued

Tested rice		Growth period (d)	Dry straw wt (kg/plot)	Av panicles/plant	Grains/panicle	Ripe state	Filled spikelets (%)	Grain yield (kg/plot)	Grain yield rank
Variety	Type ^a								
IR36	IV	134	1.50	10.5	62.6	GWFR	8.1	0.71	13
V-you 35	HV	133	1.75	10.4	59.6	GWFR	25.7	0.67	14
IR42	IV	143	3.17	8.2	103.6	GWFR	25.0	0.58	15
Wanhuaai 1	RV	141	2.00	7.7	81.0	GWFR	43.7	0.53	16
Shanyou 64	HV	132	2.66	10.3	63.5	GWFR	7.7	0.51	17
Xiangzaizao 9	RV	134	1.52	14.5	40.2	GWFR	14.4	0.45	18
Shanyou 36	HV	131	2.62	11.1	59.4	GWFR	4.2	0.35	19
Guo 16	RV	138	2.41	9.8	104.0	GWFR	16.0	0.33	20
Shanyou 63	HV	133	2.41	9.7	75.5	GWFR	11.7	0.31	21
Yuachi 231-8	RV	136	2.57	15.0	56.6	GWFR	0.5	0.24	22
IR131427-60-1-3-2-2	IV	132	2.71	13.0	57.2	GWFR	2.1	0.21	23
IR50	IV	132	2.96	14.6	60.5	GWFR	7.4	0.19	24
Liuyou 2	HV	133	2.86	7.8	60.1	GWFR	16.0	0.19	24
Ce 64	RV	133	2.87	8.7	87.6	GWFR	12.9	0.18	25
IR58	IV	132	2.58	8.1	79.3	GWFR	0.4	0.14	26
IR29725-22-3-3-3	IV	132	2.67	11.0	57.0	GWFR	2.5	0.08	27
IR9764-45-2-2	IV	145	---	---	---	GWFR	---	---	---
IR13145-45-2-3	IV	145	---	---	---	GWFR	---	---	---
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	IV	145	---	---	---	GWFR	---	---	---

^aIV = IRRI variety. ^b Green without full ripeness.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Early-maturing hybrid rice combinations

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Ten newly developed early-maturing hybrid rice combinations were tested in a six-location yield trial in the first cropping season 1986 in Hunan Province. Plot size was 13.3 m² in 3 replications. Sowing was from the end of Mar to early Apr with harvesting

date by the end of Jul.

Wei You 35 is a high-yielding combination developed in 1980. Xie Qing Zao A/Xuan 10-19 had the significantly highest yield (see table). It is moderately resistant to bacterial blight and blast. L301 A/R29, with good grain quality, was selected in Texas, USA, by Chinese scientists. Its yield is not significantly lower than that of Wei You 35. Xie Qing Zao A/Xuan 10-19 and L301 A/R29 were developed by the Hunan Hybrid Rice Research Center. □

Morphological characters, seed setting, and dry matter production of A and B lines

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Morphological characters, seed set percentage, root to straw ratio, and dry matter production were estimated in 11 cytotsterile lines of rice (A) and their maintainers (B). Five are from China, four from IRRI, and two from TNAU.

The cytotsteriles were high in total dry matter production, predominantly distributed in root and straw (see table). In general, root:straw was higher in A lines than in B lines. Plants of B lines were taller, but panicle length was greater in A lines.

The increased weight of vegetative parts in A lines may be due to the mobilization of nutrients to tillers and the prolonged vegetative phase. These, however, were not utilized by the reproductive parts because of poor sink

Growth duration and yield of newly developed early-maturing rice hybrids. Hunan, China, 1986.

Combination	Growth duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over check	Yield/d per ha (kg)
Xie Qing Zao A/Xuan 10-19	118.8	7.9	7.66 ^a	66.8
L301 A/R29	117.4	7.2	-2.37	61.4
Xie Qing Zao A/S ₅ -200	119.6	7.0	-4.44	59.0
V ₂₀ A/H 78	121.6	7.0	-5.17	57.6
Wei You 26	117.0	6.8	-7.76*	58.1
V ₂₀ A/383	117.8	6.8	-7.90*	51.8
Z 97 A/To 326	118.8	6.8	-8.14*	57.0
V ₂₀ A/305	119.0	6.7	-9.69*	56.0
V ₂₀ A/S ₅ -990	115.0	6.5	-11.57**	56.7
Chang 22 A/T 65	126.6	5.5	-24.85**	43.8
Wei You 35 (check)	120.6	7.4		61.2

^a Significant at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.